

The Molecular Compounds of 4:6-Dichloro-1:3-Dinitrobenzene.

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Sudborough and Picton, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 589-90), were the first to describe the molecular compounds of 4:6-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene with α - and β -naphthylamines. Other products of similar nature with this dichlorodinitrobenzene have now been obtained. The present paper deals with the preparation and properties of molecular compounds of the same with naphthalene, α - and β -naphthols, benzidine and pyridine. The work of Sudborough and Picton (*loc. cit.*) has also been repeated and some new interesting results have been obtained. Anthracene, dimethylaniline, diphenylamino and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines did not give any result.

It is interesting to note that in all cases except those of benzidine and pyridine the components are present in equimolecular ratios whereas the molecular compound with benzidine, contained two molecular proportions of dichlorodinitrobenzene and reverse was the case with pyridine which gave a dypyridonium compound.

The theories which have so far been advanced* in order to explain the structure, stability, colour and other characteristics of molecular compounds of various types, do not satisfy all cases and it is hoped that the experimental results in the present paper may throw some light upon this problem.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Molecular compounds of 4:6-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene (A) with naphthalene, α - and β -naphthols.—Compound A was mixed with the second component in molecular proportion and melted. The fusion curve was determined according to the method of Brady and Harris (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 494), using a Pyrex test-tube and glass-rod stirrer.

* Werner, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4329; Pfeiffer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 112, 90; Hertel and Brömer, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2446.

The molecular compounds were also prepared by mixing the components in nearly molecular proportions and crystallising the mixture from a suitable solvent. Compounds of naphthalene and α -naphthol could be obtained from benzene solution and that of β -naphthol from carbon tetrachloride. This had definite melting points and recrystallisation from the same solvents did not alter their characteristics.

Molecular compound of A with naphthalene.	Freezing point from the cool- ing curve.	m.p.	Colour and crystalline form.	Chlorine	
				Found.	Calculated.
$C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl_2$, $C_{10}H_8$ α -Naphthol	68-68.1°	68°	Pale yellow prisms.	19.5	19.3 p.c.
$C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl_2$, $C_{10}H_8O$ β -Naphthol	105°	105°	Orange plates.	18.5	18.6
** $C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl_2$, $C_{10}H_8$.	78.2-78.7°	78.5°	Deep yellow prisms.	18.6	18.6

Molecular compounds of A with α - and β -naphthylamines.

The molecular compound of α -naphthylamine was obtained in a pure state by mixing warm solutions of molecular proportions of the components in absolute alcohol and setting aside to cool. Dark brown prisms, m.p. 91°. (Found: Cl, 18.6. $C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl_2$, $C_{10}H_9N$, requires Cl, 18.7 per cent.).

If the above compound is dissolved in alcohol and the solution heated under reflux for some time the condensation product *2:4-dinitro-5-chlorophenyl- α -naphthylamine* gradually separates out. This substance was found to occur in two modifications, one yellow and the other orange. The former was obtained by recrystallising the crude substance from alcohol and benzene. The latter separates out sometimes from toluene. The orange compound gradually changes over into the yellow form between 145-50°. The yellow crystals melt at 204.05°. [Found (orange form): Cl, 10.1, in yellow form: 10.3; $C_{16}H_{10}O_4N_3Cl$, requires Cl, 10.3 per cent.]

** This compound when dissolved in benzene or absolute alcohol readily dissociated into its components.

The compound of β -naphthylamine could be obtained in a pure state by mixing solutions of the components in warm dry benzene or better in carbon tetrachloride. Dark brown silky prisms, m.p., 72-73°. (Found: Cl, 18.6. $C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl_2$, $C_{10}H_9N$, requires Cl, 18.7 per cent.).

2:4-Dinitro-5-chlorophenyl- β -naphthylamine is readily formed on heating a solution of the additive compound in alcohol and is also found to exist in two forms, one orange and the other yellow. The former is obtained from a concentrated solution of the crude material in toluene and the latter from a dilute solution. In this case the yellow variety is the labile modification. The orange compound melts at 186-87°. [Found (yellow form): Cl, 10.2, in the orange isomer, 10.2; $C_{16}H_1O_4N_3Cl$ requires Cl, 10.3 per cent.].

The molecular compound of A with benzidine.—When equimolecular quantities of A and benzidine were dissolved in ether or better in carbon tetrachloride and the solutions mixed, there was rapid separation of a small quantity of dark violet crystals. These were filtered, washed and dried at 40°. The melting point could not be determined as condensation set in on warming. The compound was found to contain 21.5 per cent. of chlorine corresponding to the formula $C_{12}H_{12}N_2, 2C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl_2$. The yield of this compound was nearly twice as much when A and benzidine were taken in the molecular ratio 2:1.

The Reaction of pyridine with compound A.—If pyridine (8g.) and A (5g.) are mixed and heated on water-bath vigorous reaction sets in with the evolution of some hydrogen chloride. The resulting brown mass was washed with ether to remove the unchanged components and extracted with cold methyl alcohol. From this extract the dipyridonium compound was precipitated out by the careful addition of ether (d 0.720). The process was repeated till the substance was obtained in the form of a colourless microcrystalline powder, yield, 2 g. (Found: C, 44.75; H, 3.84; N, 13.4; Cl, 16.44. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4N_4Cl_2, 2H_2O$ requires C, 44.53; H, 3.74; N, 13.0; Cl, 16.44 per cent.).

The water of crystallisation was not removed when the substance was kept for several days in a vacuum dessicator. The compound is very soluble in water and alcohol, but insoluble in benzene and ether. It was found to be completely ionised in aqueous solution. The melting point could not be determined because on warming it gradually changed over to a yellow compound. If the aqueous

solution is heated, a yellow crystalline substance separates on cooling and the filtrate becomes acidic.

This latter (the yellow compound) was also obtained by extracting with boiling water the residue from the original reaction mixture. It is very sparingly soluble in the usual organic solvents. It did not contain any halogen and the percentage of nitrogen was found to be 16.75. It decomposed gradually at 235°. The nature of this substance is under investigation.

The halogen estimations reported in this paper were carried out with the help of Parr's bomb according to the procedure recommended by Lemp and Broderson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2069).

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